

Structural studies on sesquiterpenoids and thiophenic acetylenes from some Asteraceae plants^Ψ

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Natural product research has evoked considerable interest among the organic chemists since 1940s. The huge volume of fascinating chemistry that has emerged from the structural studies of the vast number of natural products has enormously enriched organic chemistry. The chemistry of natural products has given rise to new ideas and concepts pertaining to stereochemistry, conformational analysis and reaction mechanism. Many complex natural products possessing multichiral centres have offered themselves as the most formidable synthetic challenge. The synthetic organic chemistry has witnessed a total revolution by achieving synthesis of many such complex phytochemicals. The development of new areas of chemical research such as biosynthesis, studies on structure activity relationship, chemotaxonomy, etc. is also a direct outcome of natural product chemistry. Structural elucidation will always be a necessary prerequisite for research in this field and with development of scientific methodology the once difficult task of elucidating the structures of relatively complex natural products has now been greatly simplified by the advent of sophisticated instrumental techniques.

Interest in natural product research can be attributed to several factors. First, unmet therapeutic needs, second the remarkable diversity of both chemical structures and biological activities of naturally occurring secondary plant metabolites, third the utility of bioactive natural products as biochemical and molecular probes, fourth the development of novel and sensitive techniques to detect biologically active natural products, fifth improved techniques to isolate, purify and structurally characterize of the active constituents and the last, advances in solving the demand for supply of complex natural products. In spite of the overwhelming influence and our dependence on modern medicines and spectacular advances in synthetic drugs, a large

segment of world's population still likes drugs from plants.

Herbal medicines have stood the test of time for their safety, efficacy, cultural acceptability and lesser side effects. The chemical constituents present in them are a part of the physiological function of living flora and hence they are believed to have better compatibility with human body. Today there are about 120 drugs of known structures that are still extracted from higher plants and used globally in allopathic medicines. These drugs produced commercially from less than 90 plant species. Since there are at least 250000 species of higher plants on earth, it is logical to presume that many more useful drugs will be found in the plant kingdom if the research for these entities is carried out in a systematic manner. Some of the prominent commercial plant derived medicines include : colchicine, camptothecin, topotecan, podophyllotoxin, etoposide, podophyllinic acid, vinblastine, vincristine, vindesine, vinorelbine, docetaxel (taxotere), paclitaxel (taxol), artemisinin, tubocurarine, pilocarpine, scopolamine, etc.

In view of the increasing importance of natural product chemistry it is intended to review our work on structural studies on sesquiterpenoids and acetylenic derivatives from *Blainvillea acmella*, *B. latifolia* and *Eclipta erecta*. The chemical investigation of the aerial parts of *Blainvillea acmella*¹ L. afforded thirteen new germacranolides including four germacrolides **1-4** and seven melampolides (acanthospermolides) **8-14** in addition to ovatifolin **5**, desacetylovatifolin **6**, desacylgrazielic acid tiglate **7** and 8 β -[2-methylbutyryloxy]-9 β -hydroxy-14-oxo acanthospermolide **15**. The structure of **1** was deduced from its ¹H NMR spectrum which was close to that of desacetylovatifolin **6**.

However, the absence of the exomethylene double bond was conspicuous. The characteristic signals of these pro-

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tions were replaced by methyl doublet and a double quartet which could be assigned by spin decoupling to H-11. The coupling of the latter clearly showed an α -oriented C-11 methyl group. The ^1H NMR spectrum of **2** was very much similar to that of **1**. The presence of the corresponding tiglate followed from the typical ^1H NMR signals and the observed downfield shift of the H-8 signal. Thus **2** was the 8-O-tiglate of **1**. The ^1H NMR spectrum of **3** differed somewhat from that of **1** though many signals were similar. The absence of an H-8 signal together with a new pair of doublets with large coupling constant below δ 3.0 clearly indicated a carbonyl group at C-8. All this agreed with the presence of desacetyl-11 β ,13-dihydroovatifolin-8-one. The structure of **4** was established from its ^1H NMR spectrum which was similar to that of ovatifolin² **5**. However, the presence of an additional oxygen function was obvious as the pair of doublets (H-9) were replaced by a doublet at δ 4.40. Fur-

thermore, the H-8 signal was shifted downfield (5.99) compared to the corresponding shift in the spectrum of ovatifolin (4.60). Typical signal of a 2-methylbutyrate indicated that this was the ester at C-8. The configuration at C-8 and C-9 positions followed from the small couplings which only agreed with a β -orientation of both oxygen functions.

The melampolide **8** did not give molecular ion and the molecular formula could be deduced from the presence of the $[\text{M}-\text{RCO}_2\text{H}]^+$ and the acyl (m/z 85) ions in the mass spectrum and the presence of a 2-methylbutyrate group according to the ^1H NMR spectrum. The other ^1H NMR spectral data strongly indicated that **8** was an isomer of **15**³. As could be deduced from the chemical shifts of H-8 and H-9, **15** and **8** differed only in the position of the ester residue. NOE difference spectroscopy indicated that the preferred conformation had both C-14 and C-15 above the plane. Clear NOEs were observed between H-15 and H-6 (15%), between H-7, H-8 (6%) and H-9 α (8%), between H-5 and H-7 (6%), between H-9, H-7 (15%) and H-2 (10%) as well as between H-14 and H-1 (15%).

The ^1H NMR spectra of **9-12** were in part very similar. The compounds **10-12** differed from each other only in the nature of the ester residue, which had to be placed at C-8 on the basis of spin decoupling. The typical ester signals showed that **10** was the acetate, **11** the tiglate and **12** the 2-methylbutyrate of **9**. The signals of **9** were in part very close to those of **8**. However, the absence of an oxygen function at C-9 led to the appearance of a pair of three-fold doublets at δ 2.62 and 2.00. On the other basis of models it was obvious that the first signal was that of H-9 α , as **8**, a W-coupling was observed between that proton (H-9 α) and H-14. Of course the absence of an ester group in **9** caused a considerable upfield shift of the signal of H-8. The ^1H NMR spectrum of **13** showed similarities to that of **9**. However, in addition to some shift differences, the absence of an H-8 signal and the downfield shifts of the signal of H-7 and H-9 showed that the corresponding 8-keto derivative was present. The ^1H NMR spectrum of **14**, whose molecular formula had two hydrogen less than **13** showed the presence of an olefinic methyl (δ 1.96d) while no signals for H-7, H-8 and H-11 were seen. The remaining signals were close to those of **13**, the presence of the 7,11-dehydro derivative of the latter is confirmed.

The extract of the roots gave stigmasterol, sitosterol, ovatifolin² **5**, the thiophene acetylenes⁴ **16** and **17**, rudbeckianone⁵ **18**, 1-hydroxy- α -curcumene and two new carotol derivatives **19** and **20**.

The extract of the aerial parts of *B. latifolia* gave subacaulin¹⁷ **21**, Zoapatanolide¹⁸ A and B (**22** and **23**) along with the new guaianolide **24** as well as the geranyl derivative^{19,20} **25**.

The structure of **24** was deduced from ¹H NMR spectrum which was close to that of dehydroleucodin²¹ and in part to that of **21**. Accordingly a 5-desoxypumilin was present. The configuration at C-8 and C-9 followed from observed couplings and the relative position of the ester group from the chemical shifts of H-8 and H-9.

The presence of cinnamic esters in **19** and **20** was established easily from their ¹H NMR spectra. The molecular formulae agreed with those of hydroxylated sesquiterpene cinnamates differing in the number of hydrogens. As followed from the ¹H NMR data at elevated temperature, **19** has two double bonds, one, according to the observed vicinal couplings, in a five membered ring and the other a trisubstituted double bond bearing a methyl group. The signal of the olefinic proton was allylically coupled to the methyl group and vicinally coupled to a proton under the oxygen function which itself showed no further coupling. All signals could be assigned by spin decoupling. The stereochemistry was deduced by NOE difference spectroscopy. The hydroxy proton showed NOEs with H-11 (3%) and H-13 (10%), H-2 with H-1 (10%) and H-14 (5%), H-4 with H-11 (3%) and H-11 with H-3 (10%), H-4 (12%), H-5 (8%) and H-7 (7%). The ¹H NMR spectrum of **20** was in part very similar to that of carotol¹⁶ and **19** but showed only one olefinic signal. All data agreed with the presence of the 2,3-dihydro derivative of **19**.

The isolation of several melampolides from *B. acmella* indicates that these compounds may be characteristic of the genus. So far such sesquiterpene lactones with an aldehyde group at C-10 and a δ 8-oxygen function have been reported from *Acanthospermum*^{7,8}, *Smallanthus*⁹, *Siegesbeckia*¹⁰ and *Ichthyothere*¹¹, while from *Melampodium*¹², *Tetragonotheca*¹³ and *Enhydra*¹⁴ similar lactones with an ester group at C-10 have been isolated. Acanthospermolides with an aldehyde group at C-10 are reported from two genera belonging to the tribe Mutisieae^{15,16}, however, these have a δ 8 α -oxygen function, a difference which may be significant also in other types of sesquiterpenes lactones. Most likely the acanthospermolides of Mutisieae are not closely related to those of the Heliantheae. The co-occurrence of melampolides and germacrolides in *Blainvillea* is an indication that enzymatic oxidation of the hydroxy group of C-14 may be accompanied by isomerization of the 1(10)-double bond.

The ¹H NMR spectrum of **25** clearly showed that derivative of geranyl geraniol or nerol was present as signals for three olefinic methyls and three oxygenated methyls were visible, two being hydroxymethylene and one an acetoxy methylene group. Now the relative position of the oxygen functions and the configurations of the double bonds have to be established. All signals were sufficiently separated in deuteriobenzene to allow spin decoupling experiments. The protons of the oxygen bearing carbons led to a broadened singlet at δ 4.10 (2H), broadened doublet at δ 4.11(2H), a pair of doublets at δ 4.90 and 4.82 (2H) and a triplet at 4.25 (1H). Furthermore, four broadened triplets at δ 5.52, 5.30, 5.35 and 5.82 were visible for olefinic protons. The irradiation at δ 5.35 sharpened the methyl singlets at 1.74 and 1.64. Accordingly, H-14 was assigned. Starting with this signal H-13 and H-12 could be determined. As the irradiation at δ 5.52 sharpened the pair of doublets and the H-12 triplet also H-18 and H-10 could be assigned. Using Gauss multiplication the coupling of H-19, H-6 and H-1 becomes clear to obtain the necessary further assignments of H-19 and H-20. NOE difference spectroscopy established the configurations of the double bonds. Clear effects were observed between H-17 and H-13 (5%), between H-16 and H-14 (10%), between H-20 and H-2 (10%), between H-18 and H-9, between H-19 and H-5 (3%) as well as between H-12 and H-10 (10%). Thus the structure of alicyclic diterpene was established.

Geranyl nerol derivatives may be characteristic for parts of the tribe Ecliptinae as these compounds have been isolated from *Aspilia*²², *Balsamorhiza*²³, *Dimerostemma*^{24,25}, *Kingianthus*²⁶, *Zexmenia*²⁷ and *Zinnia*²⁸. Guaianolides related to **24** are reported from *Balsamorhiza*²³ and *Berlandiera*¹⁷.

Re-investigation of roots and the aerial parts of *Eclipta erecta* afforded three new dithienyl derivatives²⁹⁻³¹ (**26-28**) in addition to compounds reported previously³² **29-37**. The co-occurrence of mono, di and tri thiophene derivatives is noteworthy in this species.

The structures of dithienyl esters **26-28** were deduced from their spectral data. Their UV spectra displayed broad absorption maxima at 335 nm typical of dithienyl chromophoric system and were comparable with the litera-

ture^{33,34}. The presence of acetylenic bond and ester was ascertained by observing sharp IR bands at 2240 and 1740 cm⁻¹ respectively. Their molecular formulae were arrived from high resolution mass spectrometry. The ¹H NMR spectrum of **26** showed the presence of two distinct isovalerate ester moieties. Two upfield methyl doublets at δ 0.91 and 0.95 with coupling constant 7 Hz, a pair of methylene doublets at δ 2.22 and 2.23 (*J* 7 Hz each) and a multiplet centered at δ 2.12 for methine protons indicated the presence of isovalerate functions which was further confirmed by the appearance of characteristic peaks at *m/z* 330 [M-C₄H₉COOH]⁺ and 85 [C₄H₉CO]⁺ in the mass spectrum. A set of triplets at δ 2.79 and 4.25 corresponded to adjacent =C-CH₂- and -CH₂-O protons. A singlet at δ 5.21 was assigned to -CH₂-O- group on the other side of thiophene ring. Signals in the aromatic region at δ 7.02(d), 7.00(d), 6.97(d) and 6.96(d) each with coupling constant 3.5 Hz were assignable to H-3', H-3, H-4' and H-4 protons. The sequence of protons was established by spin decoupling experiments. The ¹H NMR spectra of compounds **27** and **28** were very much similar to that of **26** barring the signals of ester functions. Pair of methyl doublets was replaced by a only doublet at δ 0.93 implying the presence of one isovalerate residue and appearance of additional signals for seneciolyloxy (δ 2.19, 1.89, 5.79) and tigloyloxy (δ 1.83, 1.80, 6.87) esters in **27** and **28** respectively, confirmed their structures. The relative position of ester moieties deduced by comparing chemical shifts of methylene groups attached to these functions with those of the corresponding diacetate from *Porophyllum*³⁴.

Biogenetically these dithienyl acetylenes are probably derived from acetylenic precursors as these still have acetylenic bonds. The key step is the addition of H₂S and its biochemical equivalent to conjugated diyne system to form a thiophene ring which is analogous to the formation of pyrrole ring by addition of NH₃ to conjugated diyne.

Addition of two equivalent of H₂S to widespread tridecapentayne **38** results in the formation of dithienyl system, which on subsequent hydrolysis, oxidation and esterification gives acetylenic esters **26-28**. Feeding experiments have established this assumption earlier for several other dithiophenes³⁵.

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